

1 **Behaviour and dispersal of mobile salmon lice when detached from the host**

2
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15 **ABSTRACT**

16
17 Sea lice can flourish when salmon are farmed in open sea-cages, necessitating treatments to control
18 outbreaks and reduce larval export. However, mobile ectoparasitic stages can be dislodged during
19 crowding or other procedures, and potentially reinfest farmed or wild fish. We studied vertical
20 movements and host-finding behaviours of mobile salmon lice (*Lepeophtheirus salmonis*) released
21 into the water column, and used those data to parameterize a biophysical dispersal model. Over 0–
22 0.4 m in tanks, larger stages sank more quickly than smaller stages (1.5 cf. 0.6 cm s⁻¹), with sinking
23 speeds of adult lice validated in deeper tanks (0–3 m) and a fjord (~15–24 m). Adult males had the
24 greatest behavioural component, sinking more slowly with host cues present and faster when dead.
25 Detached lice were able to intercept new hosts in a tank (23% within 5 min). We also investigated
26 *Caligus elongatus*, but found their strong swimming not amenable to study. A hydrodynamic dispersal
27 model indicated that detached lice can reach neighbouring cages but rarely neighbouring farms before
28 sinking below cage depth. Simulations comparing farm sites highlighted the influence of site-specific
29 current conditions on dispersal kernels, and highlighted that crowding/handling fish during favourable
30 tides can reduce downstream risk.

31
32 **Keywords:** salmon aquaculture, parasite behaviour, host finding, dispersal, reinfestation, reinfection

33 1. INTRODUCTION

34

35 Ectoparasitic salmon lice (*Lepeophtheirus salmonis*) present a major challenge for sustainable Atlantic
36 salmon (*Salmo salar*) farming throughout the north Atlantic and Pacific regions. Salmon lice occur
37 naturally in variable but typically low densities on wild salmonids. However, intensive farming in open
38 sea-cages allows severe outbreaks that impact the health and welfare of farmed fish, threaten wild
39 salmonid populations by exporting large numbers of infective larvae, and lead to direct and indirect
40 economic losses for farmers (Costello 2009, Krkošek et al. 2013, Torrissen et al. 2013, Thorstad et al.
41 2015, Overton et al. 2019, Barrett et al. 2022).

42

43 Salmon lice attach themselves to the skin or fins of the host and feed on the skin, blood and mucus,
44 in severe cases leading to osmotic stress and other concerns (Grimnes & Jakobsen 1996). Gravid
45 female lice produce fertilized eggs that develop in eggstrings until they hatch into planktonic nauplius
46 larvae. Nauplii disperse and moult into copepodid larvae that infect new hosts, before progressing
47 through five parasitic stages (Hamre et al. 2013). The final three stages—pre-adult I, pre-adult II and
48 adult—are mobile, meaning they are free to move around on the surface of the host, and in some
49 cases, transfer from one host to another, especially in aquaculture settings (Ritchie 1997, Birkeland &
50 Jakobsen 1997, Todd et al. 2000, 2005, Bui et al. 2020). Host-switching may occur voluntarily, such as
51 for mate finding (Todd et al. 2005, Bui et al. 2020), but can also occur following accidental
52 dislodgement, especially during aquaculture procedures involving fish handling that result in fish
53 rubbing against each other, nets or other equipment, for instance during crowding, size-grading,
54 transferring or harvesting (Berntsen et al. 2018, Thorvaldsen et al. 2019, Bui et al. 2020, Geitung et al.
55 2024). Moreover, most delousing treatments lead to some lice being detached but not killed, posing
56 a reinfestation risk if not collected. Detached lice are perhaps most likely to attach to a new host within
57 the same sea-cage, but more concerningly from an environmental and operational perspective, some
58 may exit the cage and encounter new hosts in neighbouring cages, neighbouring farms, or wild
59 salmonid populations (Ritchie 1997, Birkeland & Jakobsen 1997, Guttu et al. 2025).

60

61 The reinfestation risk will depend on the number of lice lost to the environment, but also the likelihood
62 of those lice remaining viable and at a suitable depth range long enough to intercept a new host.
63 Recent work shows that large numbers of lice are lost to the environment during crowding and
64 handling (Geitung et al. 2024, Guttu et al. 2025), and that detached pre-adult and adult salmon lice do
65 remain viable long enough to encounter and attach to a new host, persisting for days to weeks off the
66 host depending on the temperature (Dalvin et al. 2025). However, we otherwise lack basic information
67 on the behaviour of detached mobile stages, including whether mobile stages exhibit active swimming
68 to maintain depth, and whether this behaviour is affected by environmental conditions. Once basic
69 behaviours are quantified, hydrodynamic dispersal models can be used to investigate potential spread
70 from specific cages and farms. Similar models have been used for years to anticipate the spread of
71 larvae (Johnsen et al. 2016, Sandvik et al. 2016, Samsing et al. 2017).

72

73 Here, we investigated the sinking rates of detached mobile salmon lice in a controlled environment,
74 including whether vertical behaviour is influenced by salinity levels or the presence of chemosensory
75 host cues. We hypothesized that lice would (i) exhibit some active swimming to maintain depth, (ii)
76 sink more rapidly in brackish water due to lower water density and/or behavioural avoidance, and (iii)
77 that lice would swim more actively in the presence of host cues. To test the capacity of detached lice
78 to intercept a new host in optimal conditions, we also released some individuals into a tank containing
79 a small number of salmon smolts. Finally, we used observed sinking rates to parameterize a

80 biophysical dispersal model and simulated the dispersal of detached mobile lice with consideration of
81 site-specific hydrodynamic conditions at 13 representative farm sites.

82

83

84 **2. METHODS**

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86 **2.1 Behavioural trials**

87

88 **2.1.1 Sourcing of lice**

89

90 All lice used in this study originated from farmed salmon in Masfjorden in western Norway. Some were
91 removed directly from farmed fish during routine louse counts within sea-cages, and held in
92 incubators (as described in Hamre et al. 2009) at the Matre Aquaculture Research Station until
93 required. The incubators received a constant flow of seawater maintained at 9 °C and 34 ppt salinity.
94 These farm-sourced lice were generally used within 0–2 days of collection (maximum 7 days). The
95 remaining lice were sourced from a captive population maintained on host fish at the research station.
96 The captive population was established by collecting fertilized eggs from farmed fish in Masfjorden in
97 Jan 2023, shortly before the experiment. The eggs were incubated at 9 °C and 34 ppt salinity until
98 infective copepodid larvae had developed, which were then used to infect a tank-based salmon
99 population. The infection was performed by lowering the water level to 20 cm and pouring the larvae
100 into the tank. The water inlet and outlet were maintained, and the water level in the tanks returned
101 to normal within 10 min. Dissolved oxygen did not fall below 80% saturation. Water temperature was
102 adjusted to obtain the required developmental speed (Hamre et al. 2019), and varied from 9–15 °C
103 (34 ppt salinity throughout). As the cohort of lice developed, individual fish were netted out of the
104 tank as required, euthanized with a blow to the head, and placed in seawater. Mobile lice were gently
105 removed with forceps, sorted by sex and stage in petri dishes (9 °C, 34 ppt salinity), and then held in
106 incubators for up to 2 days before use in the behavioural trials.

107

108 To supplement the study of salmon lice, a small number of *Caligus elongatus* sea lice were also sourced
109 from a laboratory strain reared on lumpfish (*Cyclopterus lumpus*) at the University of Bergen (outlined
110 in Hamre et al. 2024). The strain originated from wild specimens collected in 2019 from Senja,
111 Northern Norway. The host lumpfish were infested as for salmon lice, with the host population
112 maintained at 9 °C and full salinity (~34 ppt) until adult lice had developed, at which point the hosts
113 were anaesthetized and adult lice were carefully removed using forceps.

114

115 Host salmon and lumpfish were monitored daily to ensure good welfare in line with permission
116 conditions (Norwegian Food Safety Authority application numbers 26020, 203748 and 275263).

117

118 **2.1.2 Experimental design and protocol**

119

120 We investigated the vertical behaviour of detached mobile stages by releasing individuals into the
121 water column, under controlled conditions, and quantifying their sinking rate. These trials were
122 conducted at 9 °C to match the temperature of the incubators, while several other factors were varied
123 to assess effects on sinking rate: salinity (24 or 34 ppt), presence of chemosensory host cues (seawater
124 taken from either an ambient or salmon-conditioned source), and presence of behaviour (live or dead
125 lice). Dead lice were produced by transferring individuals from the incubator to a 70 mL plastic
126 specimen jar, together with a small volume of water, and then warming the jar to 38 °C for 1 min using
127 a water bath (sufficient to kill all individuals while minimizing potential effects on buoyancy). Individual

128 lice were treated as experimental replicates and were only used once while alive, although some were
129 used again after being killed.

130

131 The sinking rate of every mobile stage (pre-adult I to adult) was tested over a 0–40 cm depth range in
132 white high-density polyethylene buckets (38 L, diameter of 34 cm at half depth, Rubbermaid Brute).
133 Before each trial, the bucket was filled to 40 cm with seawater of the specified salinity, with or without
134 host cues depending on the treatment group, and allowed to stand for 10 min to reduce turbulence.
135 Lice were then removed from an incubator using a disposable pipette with an enlarged opening to
136 prevent injury, and injected into the centre of the bucket, just under the surface (0–1 cm depth). The
137 behaviour of the louse was observed, and the time taken to reach the bottom of the bucket was
138 recorded. The sinking rate was calculated by dividing the elapsed time by the depth of the bucket. In
139 rare cases, sustained horizontal swimming caused a louse to reach the wall of the bucket before the
140 bottom. If the louse clung to or repeatedly contacted the wall, the trial was terminated, and the sinking
141 rate was calculated based on the elapsed time and depth at which it first contacted the wall.

142

143 Sinking rates of adult lice were also tested over 0–300 cm within a cylindrical concrete tank (6 m
144 diameter) filled to 300 cm depth with 34 ppt seawater at 9 °C. The tank was located outside the station,
145 but had a permanent tarpaulin covering that blocked natural light, with constant overhead lighting
146 (white LED work light, 5000 lm, 4000 K, 47 W: biltema.no) underneath the tarpaulin providing 100 to
147 5 $\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (LI193SA light sensor, Licor) from 10 to 300 cm depth. The seawater flow was shut off \sim 1
148 h before commencing the trial to reduce turbulence, at which point adult male and female lice were
149 transferred from incubators into specimen jars (containing water from the incubator) and then
150 released one by one into the tank. Individuals were then visually tracked using binoculars (Razor UHD
151 10x42: Vortex Optics), and the time taken to reach the bottom of the tank recorded. No individuals
152 reached the tank wall, so their sinking rate was calculated based on the time at which they first
153 contacted the tank bottom.

154

155 To validate findings from the bucket and tank trials (above) over greater depths (and pressure) in a
156 wild setting, 5 adult female lice (1 with egg strings), sourced from the same origin as above, were also
157 released into an open fjord environment (Masfjorden) in March and April 2024. Each louse was
158 transported from an incubator to the fjord in an individual plastic vial. Due to the presence of a strong
159 brackish layer at the surface, a scuba diver carried each vial to 15.5–18.0 m depth to avoid the
160 pycnocline and turbid conditions. There was an average salinity and temperature of 33 ppt and 6 °C in
161 this water mass. Each louse was released from a vial and followed by a diver (\sim 2 m away/above to
162 avoid influencing its behaviour) until it reached the seafloor at 18.0–24.4 m depth, at which point the
163 depth range and elapsed time was noted. Sinking rates in the fjord are compared graphically to those
164 in buckets and tanks, but are not formally analysed due to the small sample size.

165

166 We then investigated the capacity of detached mobile lice to intercept and reattach to a free-
167 swimming host in a tank environment. Salmon lice ($n = 22$) and *C. elongatus* ($n = 5$) were removed
168 from host fish using forceps, transferred to a pipette or small vial, and released individually into a 325
169 L white fiberglass tank (90 × 90 cm, filled to 40 cm depth) with circular flow of 34 ppt seawater at 9 °C,
170 and 2–3 salmon smolts swimming freely. Lice were released just above the water's surface, and then
171 visually tracked until either an outcome was observed, >5 min elapsed, or the individual was lost from
172 sight. Possible outcomes included the louse attaching to a host, attaching to the tank sides or bottom,
173 or exiting via the drain at the bottom of the tank. The findings are summarized graphically but not
174 formally analysed due to the small sample size.

175

176 2.1.3 Statistical analysis

177

178 Three linear models were fitted to data from the bucket and tank trials: Model 1 was designed to test
179 effects of salinity and life stage ('Salinity' and 'Stage' factors, respectively) on sinking rates, while also
180 distinguishing between the effects of louse swimming behaviour vs. buoyancy by comparing the
181 sinking rates of live and dead lice ('Status' factor). The model included full interactions between Status,
182 Stage and Salinity. An additional factor ('Source') was specified, without interactions, to account for
183 potential differences in the sinking rates of lice raised on hosts in flowthrough tanks at Matre vs. those
184 obtained from sea-cages at the nearby Knappen Solheim farm. The model was fitted using the *lm*
185 function in R (R Core Team 2023), the suitability of the model was assessed using residual plots, and
186 the results were interpreted via type II analysis of variance tables using the *car* package (Fox &
187 Weisberg 2019), followed by extraction and plotting of estimated marginal means using the *ggeffects*
188 and *ggplot2* packages (Wickham 2016, Lüdecke 2018). Model 2 was primarily designed to test whether
189 the presence of salmon host cues altered the vertical swimming behaviour of detached mobile salmon
190 lice. The model was specified with factors for the presence or absence of host cues ('Conditioning'
191 factor), Stage, and Source, with a Conditioning × Stage interaction term to test whether certain stages
192 were more responsive to host cues than others. Model 3 was designed to validate sinking behaviour
193 over 0–40 cm in the bucket by comparing stage-specific sinking rates in the bucket to sinking rates
194 observed over 0–300 cm in the concrete tank. Conditions not tested in the concrete tank were
195 removed from the dataset (pre-adult stages, brackish water, dead lice), and the model was specified
196 with factors indicating the use of a bucket or tank ('Vessel'), Stage, and a Vessel × Stage interaction.
197 Models 2 and 3 were each fitted and evaluated as per Model 1.

198

199 2.2 Dispersal modelling

200

201 2.2.1 Modelling approach

202

203 Dispersal of detached mobile salmon lice was modelled using Lagrangian Advection and Diffusion
204 Model (LADiM) particle tracking software (<https://github.com/bjornaa/ladim>). The three-
205 dimensional current fields needed for the particle tracking are provided by the ocean model system
206 NorFjords-160, which is based on the hydrodynamic ocean circulation model Regional Ocean
207 Modelling System (www.myroms.org; Shchepetkin & McWilliams 2005, Haidvogel et al. 2008).
208 NorFjords-160 is a modification of the NorKyst-800 system (Albretsen et al. 2011) with a horizontal
209 resolution of 160 m x 160 m and hydrodynamic forcing on the boundaries from NorKyst-800. The
210 model is run with 35 depth levels in a s-coordinate system, with hourly outputs to the particle tracking
211 model. For details, see Asplin et al. 2020).

212

213 Particles (lice) were programmed to behave according to an individual based model, where the
214 particles sink at a constant velocity corresponding to the mean sinking rate of a given life stage
215 observed in the present study (live lice in full salinity water without host cues added). Dispersal was
216 modelled for the stages with the highest and lowest sinking velocities (pre-adult I: 0.6 cm s⁻¹; adult
217 female: 1.5 cm s⁻¹; Table 1). Due to sinking rates (maximum 2 days to reach the ocean floor), survival
218 time was not a limiting factor. The lice were advected by the Euler-Forward advection scheme with a
219 horizontal diffusion of 0.1 m² s⁻¹ and a timestep of 60 s. The dispersion results were outputted hourly
220 and aggregated onto a grid of 32 m × 32 m. Lice positions are shown as the vertical grid cell where the
221 particles reach 30 (60) m depth, thus showing the horizontal extent of the dispersal of lice at 30 (60)
222 m depth. The number of lice presented is a relative number as it depends on the amount of particles

223 (lice) released. Thus, the dispersal results show the potential for spreading of the detached salmon
224 lice, not absolute numbers.

225

226 **2.2.2 Dispersal simulations**

227

228 Dispersal of detached mobile lice was simulated at 13 farm sites. Ten particles were released from
229 random locations within each cage of the farm every 30 min at depths of 0-2 m, from January through
230 December 2022 (the most recent year with complete modelled current fields). Seven of the 13 farms
231 (Otervika, Klungset, Hestabyneset, Gjengane, Farmannsøya, Fugløya, Ringholmen) were chosen as
232 they used submerged farming methods during 2022-2024, with a net bottom as deep as ~60 m and a
233 net roof with air-dome for swim bladder refilling (Oppedal et al. 2020, Warren-Myers et al. 2022,
234 2024). This new cage design (Nautilus: <https://www.akvagroup.com/nautilus>) represents some of the
235 deepest cages used in the industry at present and thus may have greater potential to encounter
236 detached mobile salmon lice as they drift and sink from other cages. The same 7 sites are also known
237 to have high infestation pressure (Lakseluskartet 2024), high lice levels and relatively frequent
238 delousing treatments (BarentsWatch 2024). The remaining 6 sites represent the upper and lower
239 extremes of current speed among Norwegian salmon farms, including the 3 farms (Kariskjæret,
240 Brattholmen, Torgerhaugen) with the highest mean current speeds during 2022, and 3 farms
241 (Båfjorden, Kilaneset, Ommundsteigen) with the lowest.

242

243 **2.2.3 Tidal experiments**

244

245 To investigate the variation in dispersal of lice during different times in a tidal cycle, two model setups
246 for the Otervika farm were developed. The strongest tidal currents in a fjord or fjord mouth typically
247 occur between high and low tide; the maximum incoming tidal current occurs when the tide is rising,
248 while the maximum outgoing tidal current occurs when the tide is falling. The Otervika farm is aligned
249 with the main current direction and has incoming and outgoing currents associated with the tides. We
250 extracted the tidal components (u_{tide}) of the along-fjord surface current (u) at the farm location using
251 a Python implementation (<https://github.com/wesleybowman/UTide/>) of the Matlab package UTide
252 (Codiga 2011). A high and low tidal experiment was designed by finding all times with maximum
253 incoming and outgoing tidal currents where the residual current ($u - u_{\text{tide}}$) is below a threshold of 0.04
254 ms^{-1} during the year 2022. The threshold was applied to capture conditions when the tidal current is
255 more important than the wind, pressure or stratification driven current, and resulted in 225 instances
256 with incoming current conditions where the tidal current dominated, and 261 instances with outgoing
257 current conditions. For each instance, 100 particles were released from each cage at Otervika at 0–2
258 m depth. Reported results are for particles released from the northernmost cage. A sinking velocity of
259 0.6 cm s^{-1} was used, corresponding to the mean sinking rate of live pre-adult I lice in full salinity
260 conditions without the addition of host cues (Table 1).

261

262

263 **3. RESULTS**

264

265 **3.1 Behavioural experiments**

266

267 **3.1.1 Sinking rates**

268

269 All mobile life stages of the salmon louse were negatively buoyant in both brackish and full salinity
270 seawater, whether alive or dead (Fig. 1). However, sinking rates varied significantly between life stages

271 (Model 1: Table 1 and 2). In general, the larger stages sank more quickly, with gravid adult females
272 being the fastest, followed by non-gravid adult females (Fig. 2). Most stages exhibited weak, if any,
273 vertical swimming behaviour. Anecdotally, pre-adult stages generally sank passively or swam
274 erratically and intermittently, while adult males tended to swim upwards or diagonally upwards to
275 maintain depth, and adult females either sank passively, or less often, swam downwards. During trials
276 with live lice in the bucket, adult males were also the most likely to reach the bucket wall, which
277 required the individual to swim >16 cm horizontally before reaching 40 cm depth (slope <2.5:1,
278 achieved by 8.1% of adult males, 4.4% of pre-adult II males, and <2.5% of other stages). These differing
279 behaviours presumably contributed to stage-specific differences in sinking rates between live and
280 dead lice (Model 1: Table 1 and 2), such that live and dead pre-adults sank at similar rates on average,
281 while live adult males sank slower than dead adult males, and live adult females sank faster than dead
282 adult females (Fig. 2). There was a significant interaction effect between salinity and stage (Model 1:
283 Table 1 and 2); lice generally sank faster in brackish water, although the effect was small, and the
284 reverse was observed for gravid adult females (albeit with a small sample size for this stage: Fig. 1).
285 The addition of salmon-conditioned seawater to provide chemosensory host cues increased the
286 vertical swimming behaviour of adult males, causing them to sink more slowly in the presence of host
287 cues (Fig. 3), while all other stages showed little or no change in behaviour (significant interaction
288 effect, Model 2: Table 2, Fig. 4). This stage-specific behavioural response, together with differing
289 sinking rates between live and dead adult males (Fig. 2), is consistent with a general pattern of
290 detached adult males exhibiting more active swimming behaviour than other stages. Sinking rates of
291 adult stages over 0–40 cm in a bucket were similar to those observed over 0–300 cm in concrete tanks
292 (Fig. 5), with no significant effect of vessel detected according to Model 3 (Table 2). The sinking rates
293 of adult lice tracked in the fjord also fell within the same range (Fig. 5), suggesting that the patterns
294 observed in the bucket trials may be applied, with some caution, over a greater depth range in the
295 field.

296
297 We were not able to gather usable data on sinking rates of *Caligus elongatus*, as every individual tested
298 ($n = 10$) swam strongly and remained at the surface of the bucket for at least 1 h, at which point we
299 terminated the experiment. All individuals reached the bucket wall at some point, but did not appear
300 to attach to the wall, preferring to continue swimming. Anecdotally, individuals held in incubators
301 tended to exhibit the same surface-attracted swimming behaviour for hours or days at a time, and
302 were rarely observed resting on the bottom of the incubators. This differed markedly from the
303 behaviour of salmon lice in the same settings, which unless disturbed, appeared to spend most time
304 resting by attaching to the walls or bottom of the incubator well.

305

306 **3.1.2 Host interception and attachment**

307

308 The host interception experiment demonstrated that some detached salmon lice and *C. elongatus* are
309 capable of intercepting and attaching to a new host when given sufficient opportunity. Of the 22
310 salmon lice released into a 325 L tank containing 2-3 fish, 5 successfully attached to a host within 5
311 min (23%), while a further 8 attached to another surface or continued swimming actively beyond 5
312 min and may have eventually intercepted a host if allowed more time (Fig. 6). At least 1 individual of
313 each life stage tested successfully attached to a host (1 pre-adult II female, 1 adult male, 3 adult
314 females). The remaining 9 individuals either exited via the drain (6) or were lost (3, unknown
315 outcome). All 3 adult female *C. elongatus* successfully attached to a host within 5 min, while the two
316 adult male *C. elongatus* continued swimming actively just below the surface for at least 20 min
317 (echoing their behaviour in the sinking rate experiment), at which point observations ceased (Fig. 6).

318

319 3.2 Modelled dispersal

320

321 Overall, particles representing detached mobile salmon lice mainly stay in the vicinity of the farm
322 which they are released from (Fig. 7). However, a small number (>0.15 lice m^{-2}) spread up to 1784 m
323 horizontally from the release point before reaching 30 m depth. Because pre-adults sink more slowly,
324 they dispersed farther than adult females before reaching the depth limit, with a range of 215-1784
325 m of the maximum spreading distance for pre-adults and 180-1748 m for adult females (Fig. 7, Table
326 3).

327

328 For the 7 sites with submerged cages and moderate current speeds, the range was 953-1466 m for
329 pre-adults and 736-1165 m for adult females before reaching 30 m depth (Table 3). As expected, the
330 maximum dispersal distance is greater when the depth limit is increased to 60 m, indicating that
331 submerged cages may be at greater risk. Note that in areas where the water depth is between 30 and
332 60 m, the maximum dispersal distance can be greater at 30 m than at 60 m depth (Table 3) as the
333 bathymetry restricts the dispersal distance. Spreading distance would increase (decrease) with smaller
334 (larger) density limits. The greatest dispersal distances occurred at Gjengane and Hestabyneset, farms
335 with a relatively strong current that is aligned with the direction of the farm (Table 3). Even so, only a
336 negligible number of mobile lice (<0.001 pre-adults m^{-2}) from Gjengane reached the nearest
337 neighbouring farm of Brattavika at 60 m depth. Otherwise, lice did not spread to neighbouring farms.
338 Ringholmen, where the main current is relatively strong and not aligned with the direction of the farm,
339 had the highest proportion of lice exiting the farm area before reaching the depth limit (Table 3).

340

341 A comparison of 3 sites with weak currents and 3 sites with strong currents demonstrates that
342 detached mobile lice spread up to 10× farther when the currents are strong (Table 3), with a much
343 larger proportion of lice exiting the farm area before reaching the depth limit. At the farms with weak
344 currents, 7.9-20.2 lice m^{-2} reach 30 m depth while still within the release cage, compared to <1.3 lice
345 m^{-2} at the farms with strong currents. Lice released at high current sites were also able to spread to
346 neighbouring farms, with up to 0.06 lice m^{-2} at 30 and 60 m within the neighbouring farm, although
347 this was most likely to occur when releases coincided with the highest current speeds, representing a
348 worst-case scenario. Contrary to expectations of submerged cages being at greater risk for lice
349 spreading from neighbouring cages, fewer lice are found at 60 m depth than at 30 m depth within the
350 farm itself. The risk of reinfection is therefore smaller in submerged cages within the original farm,
351 although we note that in the rare occurrence of lice reaching neighbouring farms, submerged cages
352 are at higher risk.

353

354 The tidal experiments revealed how dispersal patterns are affected by strong incoming or outgoing
355 tidal currents at Otervika, a farm with cages that are aligned along the fjord (Fig. 8). Lice released from
356 the northwestern cages (the fjord end of the farm) during strong incoming tides spread away from the
357 farm, farther into the fjord (Fig. 8, left). By contrast, lice released during strong outgoing tides were
358 more likely to reach the depth limit within the farm area (Fig. 8, right), potentially infesting fish within
359 other cages at the site. At 30 (60) m depth, the release cage during incoming tidal currents has 76%
360 (63%) fewer pre-adult lice reaching the depth limit while still within the cage than during outgoing
361 tides. The two adjacent cages at the site have 85 and 88% (82 and 57%) fewer pre-adult lice during
362 incoming than outgoing tidal currents, while the remaining cages have 86–94% (82–93%) fewer pre-
363 adult lice during strong incoming tidal currents. Similarly, lice released from the most seaward cage
364 were more likely to remain within the farm area and threaten adjacent cages during incoming tides
365 (results not shown).

366

367

368 4. DISCUSSION

369

370 Active swimming was observed among all mobile life stages of *L. salmonis*, yet no individuals resisted
371 the effect of gravity indefinitely. The predominant behaviour was passive sinking, sometimes
372 interspersed with short swimming efforts, usually horizontally or toward the surface, and especially
373 among adult males. Sinking rates broadly increased with body size, with adult females significantly
374 less buoyant than other mobile life stages. Some individuals were able to intercept and attach to a
375 new host in a tank setting. Dispersal modelling indicated that pre-adult and adult life stages typically
376 remain at suitable depths long enough to reach neighbouring cages within the same farm, while only
377 a small proportion of pre-adult lice have any chance of reaching neighbouring farms before sinking
378 too deep.

379

380 Factors affecting sinking rates

381

382 Sinking rates varied widely, both within and between life stages. Pre-adults (both sexes) and adult
383 females were relatively passive, with only small differences in mean sinking rates between live and
384 dead individuals, indicating that morphological or physiological differences (affecting buoyancy
385 and/or drag) may explain most of the variation in sinking rates among those life stages. By contrast,
386 the importance of live/dead status and presence/absence of host cues for adult males reflects a
387 greater influence of swimming behaviour on sinking rates. This is consistent with the current
388 understanding of salmon louse reproductive ecology, wherein females mate singly and can experience
389 mate limitation at low infestation densities (Ritchie et al. 1996, Stormoen et al. 2013, Cox et al. 2017),
390 driving adult males to switch hosts to search for unmated or other reproductively active females
391 and/or avoid competition from other males (Ritchie et al. 1996, Connors et al. 2011, Stephenson
392 2012). Adult males are presumably adapted to finding and attaching to new hosts as part of this
393 process, and so may pose a greater reinfestation risk than other life stages. Tank-based experiments
394 have found that pre-adult I lice will also switch hosts in response to high infestation densities on the
395 initial host, and that pre-adult II males will do so to search for females (Connors et al. 2011), although
396 it is not clear how widespread these behaviours are. Those stages did not exhibit obvious host-finding
397 behaviours in the present study, with similar sinking rates with and without host cues present.

398

399 We expected that lice would sink faster in brackish water, primarily due to the reduced buoyancy of
400 objects in brackish water, but perhaps also a behavioural component in which lice attempt to avoid
401 an osmotically stressful brackish layer (Andrews & Horsberg 2020) by sinking into a more saline water
402 mass below, as has been observed in larval salmon lice (Crosbie et al. 2019). We did find the expected
403 effect of salinity on sinking rates, but the effect was no more apparent for live lice than dead lice,
404 suggesting that there is minimal behavioural avoidance of brackish water. This may reflect a lack of
405 natural selection for such a response, as mobile lice are typically attached to a host and may be better
406 served by remaining attached to that host for as long as possible, rather than detaching in the hope
407 of finding a new host in a more saline water mass.

408

409 Salmon lice exhibited some attraction to surfaces, including to the walls of the incubator, bucket or
410 tank. Adult males were the stage most likely to reach the bucket wall and attach (sometimes for a few
411 seconds, sometimes indefinitely), followed by pre-adult II males. If this is a widespread behaviour in a
412 sea-cage environment, then it is possible that lice will attach to crowding nets, net pens or other
413 underwater structures. This complicates potential dispersal dynamics by allowing lice to pause their
414 dispersal, or if they attach to moving objects such as the hull of a wellboat or barge, potentially

415 increase their dispersal distance or allow upstream dispersal. A similar risk has also been hypothesised
416 for farm-associated wild fish based on observations of mobile salmon lice attached to saithe (Bruno &
417 Stone 1990, Lyndon & Toovey 2001) and frequent movements of the same species between farm sites
418 (Uglem et al. 2009).

419

420 **Dispersal dynamics**

421

422 At the average salmon farm, mobile lice released in the surface layer of a sea-cage pose a clear risk to
423 the same or other cages at the same farm, and in areas with strong tidal currents and closely spaced
424 farms, neighbouring farms may also be at risk. However, the tidal experiments highlighted the
425 potential benefits of timing crowding or other handling events to coincide with favourable current
426 conditions. Where logistically feasible (e.g., minimal downtime for delousing vessels), planning around
427 tide times could eliminate the spread of mobile lice between farm sites, even at locations with high
428 current speeds. In practice, delousing in very strong water current conditions is impractical and rarely
429 carried out, meaning existing practices may already be mitigating the risk of between-farm
430 transmission. Low-current sites have a larger potential for reinfesting cages within the farm itself, but
431 the risk of reinfesting neighbouring farm sites is very low.

432

433 The year-long dispersal experiments included a wide range of current scenarios, including louse
434 particles being released during storms, when farms would likely not be delousing. This will have
435 inflated the maximal dispersal distances observed. However, a counterpoint is that no turbulence or
436 resuspension (lifting lice from the seabed back into the water column) is included in the dispersal
437 modelling. Even without resuspension, incorporation of turbulence could increase the variance (and
438 range) of dispersal distances, thus increasing the maximum dispersal distance, although lice sink
439 relatively quickly and the effect is therefore expected to be small. Accordingly, a month-long sensitivity
440 test with vertical turbulence of $10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, a large number for stratified fjords, found an increase in
441 the maximum dispersal distance of only 1%, with most lice still remaining within the original farm.
442 Resuspension would probably not be influential at deep sites, but at shallower sites, resuspension
443 from the bottom, together with strong mid-depth currents, could disperse the lice further at depths
444 aligned with open farms.

445

446 It is also important to note that the reported density values are relative, depending on the number of
447 lice released at each 30-min interval. As such, these values should be used to inform the potential
448 dispersal kernel of detached lice, not the precise number of lice that are expected to reach a given
449 farm.

450

451 **Evolutionary implications**

452

453 Most salmon lice in Norwegian waters exist on farmed rather than wild salmon, and as a result,
454 selective processes occurring within farms have the potential to drive the evolution of salmon lice in
455 ways that would be maladaptive on wild hosts (Dempster et al. 2021, Coates et al. 2021). Detachment
456 and host-switching may be one such example. Wild hosts are expected to select for strong attachment,
457 as lice are relatively safe on the host, and the low density of hosts in the environment means that lice
458 are unlikely to find another if they detach. By contrast, the high density of hosts within sea-cages will
459 likely reduce the fitness cost of detaching, and may therefore select for weaker attachment or
460 voluntary detachment, especially if there are costs to being strongly attached. For instance, strong
461 attachment may come at the cost of mobility on the host (adult males are more mobile on the host
462 and more likely to be dislodged during handling: (Stephenson 2012, Cox et al. 2017, Bui et al. 2020)),

463 while voluntary host-switching behaviour—to find mates or avoid competition—is more likely to pay
464 off when hosts are abundant. Frequent delousing treatments may also be an important selective
465 process, as lice that remain attached to their host through pre-treatment crowding are likely to be
466 collected/killed by the delousing treatment, whereas those that are dislodged during crowding can
467 evade the treatment and potentially find a new host in a neighbouring cage. If entering a delousing or
468 harvesting vessel is certain to cause mortality, then being dislodged during pre-treatment crowding
469 would be beneficial so long as there is a non-zero probability of finding a new host outside the
470 crowding net. More work is needed to understand these dynamics, but if such evolutionary change is
471 undesirable, it should be a priority to collect lice that detach during crowding (Geitung et al. 2024).

472

473 **Biosecurity implications**

474

475 Lice that feed on and move between multiple hosts could act as a vector for pathogens, either by
476 feeding on infected tissues or by carrying the pathogen externally. Salmon lice have been reported to
477 carry a range of pathogens of concern for salmon aquaculture, including viruses (infectious salmon
478 anaemia virus and salmon alphavirus: Nylund et al. 1991, 1993, Petterson et al. 2009), bacteria
479 (*Aeromonas salmonicida*, *Tenacibaculum maritimum*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Vibrio* spp.: Nese &
480 Enger 1993, Barker et al. 2009) and microsporidian fungi (*Desmozoon* spp.: Freeman & Sommerville
481 2009). Jakob et al. (2011) found that salmon lice acquired infectious haematopoietic necrosis virus
482 (IHNV) by feeding on infected hosts, remained virus-positive for 12 h, and passed on the virus when
483 allowed to attach to a naïve host. Later, Novak et al. (2016) reported that salmon lice acquired the
484 bacterium *Aeromonas salmonicida* by feeding on infected hosts and sometimes transferred it to naïve
485 hosts, although only under certain conditions. Based on available evidence, detached mobile lice
486 should be considered a potential (but perhaps unlikely) vector for salmonid diseases and managed
487 accordingly, especially if dispersal to neighbouring farms is a possibility. Transport on vessels or wild
488 fish could increase the likelihood of dispersal between farms (Bruno & Stone 1990, Lyndon & Toovey
489 2001, Uglem et al. 2009), although more data are required to assess this risk (Uglem et al. 2014).

490

491 **Conclusion**

492

493 Together, these findings indicate that mobile salmon lice detached during crowding or delousing
494 procedures do pose a risk of reinfestation, but mainly within the farm of origin. Any transmission of
495 mobile lice between neighbouring farms would have biosecurity implications, especially if lice function
496 as a vector for salmon pathogens. Methods to collect lice that detach during farm procedures will
497 reduce the number of lice that escape the farm and thus minimise the associated biosecurity concerns.
498 Based on our preliminary observations of (non)sinking rates in buckets and host interception in small
499 tanks, *Caligus elongatus* have much greater potential for dispersal and reinfestation, although a
500 targeted experiment, perhaps undertaken in the field, is required to better understand the risks posed
501 by this species.

502

503

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505

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Available upon request.

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Table 1. Summary of observed sinking rates of salmon louse life stages according to the environment (vessel), live/dead status, salinity, and chemosensory cues (conditioning).

Vessel	Stage	Status	Salinity (ppt)	Conditioning	n	Mean sinking rate (cm/s)	SD	SE
Bucket	Pre-adult I	Alive	24	Ambient	23	0.79	0.17	0.03
			34	Ambient	39	0.57	0.18	0.03
				Salmon	28	0.49	0.22	0.04
		Dead	24	Ambient	20	0.51	0.25	0.06
			34	Ambient	50	0.50	0.21	0.03
	Pre-adult II female	Alive	24	Ambient	21	0.85	0.30	0.06
			34	Ambient	60	0.65	0.25	0.03
				Salmon	42	0.66	0.26	0.04
		Dead	24	Ambient	21	0.80	0.21	0.05
			34	Ambient	58	0.61	0.27	0.04
	Pre-adult II male	Alive	24	Ambient	27	0.67	0.19	0.04
			34	Ambient	53	0.57	0.22	0.03
				Salmon	12	0.53	0.23	0.07
		Dead	24	Ambient	25	0.44	0.17	0.03
			34	Ambient	61	0.51	0.28	0.04
	Adult male	Alive	24	Ambient	22	0.89	0.36	0.08
			34	Ambient	68	0.76	0.47	0.06
				Salmon	39	0.52	0.39	0.06
		Dead	24	Ambient	22	1.11	0.34	0.07
			34	Ambient	84	1.05	0.16	0.02
Adult female	Alive	24	Ambient	27	1.65	0.42	0.08	
		34	Ambient	62	1.55	0.61	0.08	
			Salmon	32	1.50	0.31	0.05	
	Dead	24	Ambient	19	1.73	0.39	0.09	
		34	Ambient	61	1.54	0.37	0.05	
Adult female (ovi.)	Alive	24	Ambient	4	1.38	0.19	0.09	
		34	Ambient	10	1.79	0.55	0.18	
			Salmon	11	1.69	0.38	0.11	
	Dead	24	Ambient	4	1.23	0.05	0.03	
		34	Ambient	10	1.54	0.28	0.09	
Tank	Adult male	Alive	34	Ambient	5	0.58	0.35	0.16
	Adult female	Alive	34	Ambient	7	1.36	0.48	0.18
	Adult female (ovi.)	Alive	34	Ambient	12	1.63	0.19	0.06
Fjord	Adult female	Alive	33	Ambient	4	1.25	0.34	0.17
	Adult female (ovi.)	Alive	33	Ambient	1	1.37	–	–

Table 2. Analysis of variance tables (type II) corresponding to Models 1 and 2. Model terms include: Status = alive or dead (2 levels); Stage = pre-adult I, pre-adult II male, pre-adult II female, adult male, non-gravid adult female, gravid adult female (6 levels); Salinity = 24 or 34 ppt (2 levels); Source = sea-cage or tank-based host population (2 levels); Conditioning = ambient or salmon-conditioned seawater (2 levels); Vessel = 40-cm deep bucket or 3-m deep concrete tank (2 levels).

Model 1				
Term	SS	df	F	p
Status	0.01	1	0.10	0.72
Stage	74	5	189	<0.0001
Salinity	3.9	1	50	<0.0001
Source	12	1	151	<0.0001
Status × Stage	4.8	5	12	<0.0001
Status × Salinity	0.2	1	3.0	0.083
Stage × Salinity	2.1	5	5.4	0.0001
Status × Stage × Salinity	0.5	5	1.2	0.29
Residuals	64	824		
Model 2				
Term	SS	df	F	p
Conditioning	0.3	1	3.1	0.08
Stage	58	5	109	<0.0001
Source	3.2	1	30	<0.0001
Conditioning × Stage	1.2	5	2.3	0.041
Residuals	47	441		
Model 3				
Term	SS	df	F	p
Vessel	0.35	1	1.8	0.17
Stage*	24	2	63	<0.0001
Vessel × Stage*	0.01	2	0.04	0.96
Residuals	30	156		

* Adult stages only

Table 3. Overview of findings from dispersal modelling runs where 10 particles (lice) are released from 13 farm sites every 30 min through the year 2022. Site characteristics include group (the reason for inclusion in the simulation), farm layout (number of rows × cages per row), farm direction (along the cage rows), main current direction, and the mean (max) current at 15 m depth. Lice were released from each cage in the farm, with each release investigated separately. Outcomes are the maximum values resulting from a release from a single cage, and are reported by life stage and depth threshold, with values for 30 m not in parenthesis, values for 60 m in parentheses (omitted if the site is shallower than 60 m), values for pre-adult I and pre-adult II males in *italics*, and values for adult females in **bold**. Four outcomes are reported: the relative amount (as a density) of lice reaching the depth threshold within the release cage, reaching the depth threshold within a neighbouring cage, reaching the depth threshold within the farm area, and the maximum distance where >0.15 lice m⁻² are found at the threshold depth.

Farm	Group	Farm layout	Farm direction	Main current direction	Mean (max) current @ 15 m (cm s ⁻¹)	N. lice release cage (lice m ⁻²)	N. lice neighbouring cage (lice m ⁻²)	N. lice farm (lice m ⁻²)	Distance (m)
Otervika	Sub. farming	2×4	NEE/SWW	NEE/SW	7.2 (52.9)	1.6 (0.8) 3.5 (2.3)	1.6 (0.8) 3.6 (2.5)	0.7 (0.5) 1.0 (0.9)	1128 (1241) 884 (952)
Klungset	Sub. farming	2×5	NEE/SWW	NEE/SW	8.6 (68.2)	1.8 (0.9) 4.1 (3.2)	1.6 (0.8) 3.8 (3.0)	1.0 (0.6) 1.5 (1.4)	972 (1112) 828 (890)
Hestabyneset	Sub. farming	1×6	NNW/SSE	NW	9.3 (50.3)	1.2 (0.6) 2.5 (1.6)	1.4 (0.6) 2.6 (1.6)	0.7 (0.4) 0.9 (0.7)	1268 (1601) 1006 (1167)
Gjengane	Sub. farming	1×6	N/S	N/S	8.7 (47.0)	1.0 (0.5) 2.4 (1.6)	1.2 (0.5) 2.6 (1.7)	0.6 (0.4) 0.9 (0.8)	1466 (1537) 1165 (1236)
Farmannsøya	Sub. farming	2×5	NNE/SSW	NEE/SW	10.5 (58.2)	0.4 (0.2) 1.3 (1.0)	0.4 (0.2) 1.0 (0.8)	0.4 (0.2) 0.7 (0.6)	1140 (585) 1039 (1001)
Fugløya	Sub. farming	2×6	NE/SW	WNW/ESE	7.7 (81.6)	5.8 (1.6) 12.3 (5.0)	2.7 (1.6) 5.3 (3.9)	0.6 (0.2) 0.9 (0.6)	1171 (719) 736 (636)
Ringholmen	Sub. farming	2×8	NE/SW	NW/ESE	12.3 (57.1)	0.4 (0.2) 0.9 (0.7)	0.4 (0.2) 1.0 (0.7)	0.1 (0.1) 0.2 (0.2)	953 (775) 921 (1163)
Båfjorden	Low current	1×3	NNE/SSW	N/S	1.1 (8.3)	7.9 13.8	1.8 0.7	1.1 1.5	215 196
Kilaneset	Low current	2×2	NNW/SSE	NNW/SSE	1.3 (12.0)	14.5 20.2	0.8 1.9	3.3 3.3	223 180

Ommundsteigen	Low current	2×3	NW/SE	WNW/ESE	1.3 (14.0)	11.3 (7.7) 20.0 (17.5)	7.3 (4.4) 7.8 (7.7)	2.9 (2.6) 3.2 (3.2)	348 (412) 223 (223)
Kariskjæret	High current	2×5	NE/SW	NEE/SW	20.4 (93.9)	0.2 0.7	0.16 0.65	0.17 0.63	1017 878
Brattholmen	High current	2×6	NNE/SSW	N/S	21.5 (137.0)	0.3 1.3	0.37 1.63	0.5 1.15	1050 1436 (1499)
Torgerhaugen	High current	1×1	NEE/SWW	NE/SW	26.7 (91.7)	0.3 0.8		0.23 0.51	1784 1748 (1836)

Figure 1. Histograms comparing the distribution of sinking rates of live and dead mobile salmon lice (PA1 = pre-adult I, PA2M = pre-adult II male, PA2F = pre-adult II female, AM = adult male, AF = adult female, AFE = gravid adult female) in brackish or full salinity seawater (24 or 34 ppt). Sinking rates were measured from 0–40 cm depth in a white bucket with artificial white lights overhead. The vertical dashed line shows the mean sinking rate corresponding to each panel.

Figure 2. Predicted sinking rates (estimated marginal means \pm 95% confidence intervals from Model 1) of live and dead mobile salmon lice (PA1 = pre-adult I, PA2M = pre-adult II male, PA2F = pre-adult II female, AM = adult male, AF = adult female, AFE = gravid adult female). Sinking rates were measured over 0-40 cm depth in 34 ppt seawater without the addition of any host cues.

Figure 3. Histograms comparing the distribution of sinking rates of live mobile salmon lice (PA1 = pre-adult I, PA2M = pre-adult II male, PA2F = pre-adult II female, AM = adult male, AF = adult female, AFE = gravid adult female) with or without the addition of salmon-conditioned seawater to provide a chemosensory host cue. Sinking rates were measured from 0–40 cm depth in a white bucket with 34 ppt salinity and artificial white lights overhead. The vertical dashed line shows the mean sinking rate corresponding to each panel.

Figure 4. Predicted sinking rates (estimated marginal means \pm 95% confidence intervals from Model 2) of live mobile salmon lice (PA1 = pre-adult I, PA2M = pre-adult II male, PA2F = pre-adult II female, AM = adult male, AF = adult female, AFE = gravid adult female) with or without the addition of salmon-conditioned seawater to provide a chemosensory host cue. Sinking rates were measured from 0–40 cm depth in a white bucket with 34 ppt salinity and artificial white lights overhead.

Figure 5. Histograms showing similar sinking rates among live mobile salmon lice released into 40-cm deep buckets, a 3-m deep concrete tank, or >15 m depth in a fjord. Only adult stages were released into the concrete tank: AM = adult male, AF = adult female, AFE = gravid adult female. Bucket and tank trials were conducted with 34 ppt salinity and 9 °C, without the addition of any host cues, and with artificial overhead lighting (white light). The fjord trial was conducted at 33 ppt and 6 °C. The vertical dashed line shows the mean sinking rate corresponding to each panel.

Figure 6. Outcomes from host interception trials in which detached mobile stages of *Caligus elongatus* and *Lepeophtheirus salmonis* were released into a 600-L tank containing Atlantic salmon smolts. Outcomes are given by species and stage (PA2F = pre-adult II female, AM = adult male, AF = adult female).

Figure 7. Simulated dispersal of salmon lice with a sinking rate of 0.6 cm s^{-1} , representing pre-adult 1 and pre-adult 2 male lice released in batches of 10 lice every 30 min over the year 2022. The red gradient indicates the aggregated density of lice at 30 m depth over the year 2022. The farm area is shown in black, while the blue circles show the position of the cages. The white line denotes $0.15 \text{ pre-adult lice m}^{-2}$ at 30 m depth, the green line denotes $0.15 \text{ pre-adult lice m}^{-2}$ at 60 m depth, and the pink line denotes $0.15 \text{ adult female lice m}^{-2}$ at 30 m depth (the latter assuming a sinking rate of 1.5 cm s^{-1}).

Figure 8. Simulated dispersal of salmon lice according to tidal current conditions. The red gradient indicates the aggregated density at 30 m depth, assuming a sinking rate of 0.6 cm s^{-1} (representing pre-adult 1 and pre-adult 2 male lice) for release times during strong incoming tidal currents (left panel) and strong outgoing tidal currents (right panel). The black line delineates the farm area, while the circles show the position of the cages. The green circle denotes the cage from which the particles were released.